

COOPERATION OF PARENTS AND SCHOOL IN EDUCATION OF CHILDREN IN PRIMARY GRADES

Kudyarova Artikgul

*Student of the Faculty of primary education of
The Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz*

Abstract. This article talks about the importance of cooperation between parents and school in raising children in primary grades. The author draws attention to the fact that such cooperation is the main factor in the successful study and development of children in primary classes. At first, the author dwells on the role of parents in raising children. He said that parents are the first teachers of their children and play an important role in their education.

Keywords: parent cooperation, school and family, raising children in primary school.

INTRODUCTION

Education of children in primary school is carried out between parents and school through consultations, open classes or online communication platforms. Parents have the opportunity to receive information about their child's curriculum, grades, and behavior, as well as to discuss issues that interest them.

Parents can also contribute to their children's education by helping them with their schoolwork and projects. Communicating with children during homework

helps to improve their motivation and academic performance. Parents can also supplement the learning experience by offering additional materials or visiting museums, exhibits, and other educational activities.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Cooperation between parents and the school allows students to identify and solve problems or difficulties that arise in time. Parents can support children who are struggling to adapt to a new classroom, help them overcome conflict or stress, and find solutions together with the teacher [3].

Useful aspects of cooperation between parents and school in raising children in primary school:

Improving learning: When parents and schools work together, they can create an appropriate and supportive environment for children to learn. Parents can support their children's homeschooling efforts and help them with homework, as well as work with teachers to identify each child's individual needs.

RESULTS

Promoting psychological well-being: cooperation between parents and schools helps to create a healthy psychological environment for children. When parents and teachers work together, they can address a child's emotional problems, improve self-esteem, and develop social interactions.

Greater understanding of the child's needs: Parents know their children best, so their involvement in the educational process allows for a deeper understanding of the child's needs and interests. They can share information about the child's home environment, preferences, and characteristics, which can help teachers better tailor

learning and positively influence the child's success and self-determination in the educational environment [1].

Participation in decision-making: the partnership between parents and the school allows parents to actively participate in joint decision-making about important aspects of the child's education and development. They can participate in conferences, meetings, committees to share their thoughts and ideas.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Harmful aspects of cooperation between parents and school in raising children in primary school:

Lack of time: Parents may find it difficult to attend school activities due to their commitments, such as work or other family commitments. This can lead to limitations in cooperation and affect the effectiveness of the educational process.

Conflicts between parents and teachers: Sometimes parents and teachers may have different views and approaches, which can lead to conflict and confusion. Parents may have their own ideas about how best to educate their children, which may conflict with the school's teaching methods [5].

Lack of communication: Poor communication between parents and the school can be an obstacle to effective cooperation. If parents and teachers do not keep each other informed of problems, achievements or changes, this leads to misunderstanding and failure in the child's learning and development.

Parental Overload: In some cases, parents are overwhelmed with the demands of participating in all activities and distractions from their responsibilities and self-care. will be

From the aspects mentioned above, it can be understood that the partnership between parents and the school is a mutually beneficial partnership that requires mutual respect, open communication and flexibility on both sides.

Cooperation between parents and the school in the education of children in primary school is based on the following principles:

Mutual cooperation: Parents and the school cooperate equally, share information and participate in the child's education.

Openness and transparency: Parents and the school share information about the child's achievements and problems, organizational issues and teaching methods.

CONCLUSIONS

Proven Practices: Parents and schools use proven practices and methodologies and implement innovative approaches based on mutually beneficial partnerships.

Stability and consistency: By working together to support a child's development, parents and schools provide stability and consistency in education.

Development of cooperation: Parents and schools strive to constantly develop mutual cooperation, increase their knowledge and skills in the field of children's education.

These principles help parents and schools to effectively cooperate in the education of their children, to create a favorable environment for their development and success. Based on the above information, it can be concluded that child education is important not only for parents, but also for the school community. Because it is important to start the education of a child from the primary school in order to raise a young generation who is mature in all aspects. Therefore,

establishing cooperation between school and parents in child education is the basis of raising perfect people.

REFERENCES

1. Education in primary education. Education is a methodical complex. Bukhara 2022.
2. ЕРМАТОВА, Р. О. (2018). УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ВРЕМЕННЫМ УЧЕНИЕМ ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ С ОБУЧЕНИЕМ ИНВАЛИДЫ. *Наука среди нас*, (7), 85-88.
3. Ermatova, R. O. (2018). ADVANTAGES OF THE TECHNIQUE" WHAT/HOW/WHY OUTLINES" IN DEVELOPING PRODUCTIVE SKILLS OF THE MEDICAL STUDENTS. *Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук*, (6), 69-71.
4. Utegenova, S., & Rozumova, D. (2024). DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING TAX AUDIT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6).
5. Utegenova, S., & Mirzabaeva, U. (2024). TODAY'S IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF AUDIT ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 4(6), 93-95.
6. Utegenova, S., & Oralbaeva, F. (2024). O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotiga xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimini oshirishda mamlakatning investitsion muhiti jozibadorligini oshirish. *Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана*, 1(6), 131-134.
7. Khasanova, S., Akisheva, N., & Zholayeva, M. (2023). Methodological aspects of tax planning in the context of sustainable development. *Revista Gestão & Tecnologia*, 23(3), 286-298.
8. Маматқулов, Б. М., & Нематов, А. А. (2021). Ўзбекистон Республикаси аҳолиси орасида COVID-19 тарқалишининг хусусиятлари.
9. Abdullayeva, N. (2023). AHMAD YASSAWI SECT: THE ISSUE OF ZIKR AND THE STATUS OF ZAKIR. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 438-440.
10. Bazarov, S. (2024). JURNALIST VA BLOGERLAR NUTQI ETIKASI. *Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика*, 3(1), 36-39.

11. Norqulovich, S. H. (2023, October). NURILLO CHORINING BADIY ASARLARIDA MILLIY KOLORITGA XOS KO 'RINISHLAR NUTQIY JIHATDAN IFODALANISHI. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 25-29).
12. Ziyodullayeva, M., & Muxtorova, M. (2024). ABDULLA QODIRIY HAYOTI VA IJODIGA AYRIM CHIZGILAR. *NRJ*, 1(3), 860-863.
13. Muxtorova, M. (2024). MAXTUMQULI SHE'RIYATIDA AYTISHUV: AN'ANA VA IZDOSHLIK. *NRJ*, 1(3), 254-257.
14. Tajenova, G., Turdiyeva, G., Qurbanov, A., & Isakov, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Аpxue научных исследований*, (14).
15. Janabay, I., Gulbahar, T., Gulayda, T., Alisher, Q., & Ilkhambek, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the republic of uzbekistan. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(8), 1684-1693.
16. Turdieva, G., Abishov, M., & Muratbaev, I. (2024). THE IMPACT OF CREDIT RISKS ON AN EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION IN THE FINANCIAL SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS. *NRJ*, 1(4), 215-225.
17. Beglenov, N., & Muratbaev, I. (2023). HOTEL SERVICES AS AN OBJECT OF STRATEGIC MARKETING ORIENTED TO THE CONSUMER. *Science and Education in Karakalpakstan*, 32(2), 175-177.
18. Xalmuratovich, B. S. (2024). JAHON AMALIYOTIDA AGROKLASTER TIZIMINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH VA YURITISH BO 'YICHA TO 'PLANGAN TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI. *Scientific Journal of Actuarial Finance and Accounting*, 4(04), 140-150.
19. Bayjanov, S. X., & Abishov, M. S. (2024). DEVELOPING THE ACTIVITY OF JOINT STOCK COMPANIES BY IMPROVING DIVIDEND POLICY. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 3(3), 94-97.
20. Sultanov, B., Nurimbetov, T., Bayjanov, S., Seyilbekov, B., & Durmanov, A. (2023, October). Trends in change and the current state of the effectiveness of land reclamation measures in agriculture. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2921, No. 1). AIP Publishing.

21. Байжанов, С. Х. (2023). ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ В СЕЛЬСКОЕ ХОЗЯЙСТВО НОВОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(4), 51-53.
22. Omonovna, E. R. (2023). KLINIK ATAMALAR SHAKLLANTIRISHDA SUFFIKSATSIYA USULI VA TA 'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARI. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 9(3), 198-204.
23. Shodiyeva, G. (2024). O 'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILIDA SO 'ZLARNI TURKUMLARGA AJRATISH MASALALARI. *Interpretation and researches*, (4 (26)).
24. qizi Tursunova, M. A., & qizi Shodiyeva, G. N. (2023). MAIN INFLUENTIAL FACTORS TO LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(3 SPECIAL), 1181-1183.
25. Aliyeva, N., & qizi Shodiyeva, G. N. (2023). Ingliz Tilida So 'Z Turkumlari Tasnifi Masalalari Sharhi. *Scholar*, 1(13), 22-27.
26. Navruza, A. (2023). INGLIZ TILI MORFOLOGIYASIDA SOZ TURKUMLARINI ORGANISH ZARURIYATI. *ITALY" ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN THE FACE OF MODERN CHALLENGES"*, 14(1).
27. Nishonov U., Tursunov I. "Course of Pedagogy" Tashkent 2017.